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Tribological effects of the geometrical properties of plasma spray coatings partially melted by laser

A. García, M. Cadenas, M. R. Fernández, A. Noriega

University of Oviedo. Department of Construction and Manufacturing Engineering. University of Oviedo, Gijón, Asturias, Spain. * Phone: +34-985181925 Email: garciamaralberto@uniovi.es

Abstract

The tribological behaviour of NiCrBSi plasma spray coatings partially melted by laser was investigated. Partial melting provides dual property surface coatings: melted areas, with a homogenous microstructure; and plasma spray areas, with porosity and cracks. This paper studies the influence of two geometrical properties of the partially melted surfaces: the angle of the laser tracks, and the ratio of the melted surface. Laser melting was performed using a 1700W CO₂ laser and wear tests were carried out using a block-on-ring tribometer in pure sliding lubricated contact.

The main wear mechanism and the interaction of the geometrical properties of the coating are discussed in this paper. The results of wear tests indicate that the best percentage of melted surface to reduce the wear rate is 46%, whereas the track angle is not found to be a major factor influencing the wear rate. The study of Coefficient of Friction (COF) reveals that low track angles have the lowest friction and that the percentage of melted surface is not a major factor influencing the COF.

Keywords: Thermal spray coatings; Laser processing; Lubricated wear; Ni alloys.

1. Introduction

Plasma spray technique is widely used in industry to manufacture coatings for different purposes, such as thermal barrier [1, 2] or increase the wear resistance of materials [3]. The wear behaviour of coatings of this type has been studied for different coating materials and different substrates over the last few decades [4, 5], although ceramic coatings are most frequently [6-9]. The success of the industrial uses of atmospheric plasma spraying (APS) is motivated by the good quality of the coatings obtained and low cost compared to other techniques such as laser cladding.

Ni alloys are one of the most widely used materials to obtain anti-wear coatings due to the balance they present between moderate hardness, low brittleness, good corrosion resistance and a relatively low price compared to other materials. For this reason, Ni alloy coatings are suitable for a broad range of contact configurations in industry. The final characteristics of Ni alloy coatings depend on the specific composition of the alloy (Chromium is usually added between 4% and 16 % to increase hardness and corrosion resistance) and the technique used to obtain the coating [10].

Despite the high temperatures generated by the APS process, some of the powder material does not melt completely and, as result, a non-homogenous relatively high porosity coating is formed. Moreover, due to

the non-melting process, the adherence between coating and substrate is poor, because metallurgical bonding does not occur. These features result in a worsening of the tribological behaviour in comparison with other techniques such as laser cladding, due to the decrease in the average hardness of the coating, and the increase in brittleness and the risk of stripping [11]. However, the plasma spray process provides coatings with certain advantages with respect to other techniques. One of these is the low deformation induced in the substrate during the process, owing to the fact that the substrate is not melted. This technique thus allows high dimensional accuracy parts to be obtained with low residual stress [12, 13]. Porosity in coatings may be an advantage for lubricated contacts, because it acts like a textured surface, retaining the lubricant under a mixed and limit lubrication regime [14].

A well-known post-treatment technique consists in melting the coating with a heat source, such as an oxy-fuel flame or laser beam [15]. Complete melting of the coating reduces the porosity and increases the homogeneity of the coating, as well as improving the adherence between substrate and coating. Several authors have researched the laser melting post-process with the aim of improving the wear behaviour of plasma spray coatings. Serres et al. [12, 16] studied the microstructure of a hybrid plasma spray process which uses a laser diode to melt the coating surface just after plasma spray deposition. Similarly, Felgueroso et al. [17] proposed a partial laser melting process to reduce the cost of the complete melting process and preserve part of the characteristic plasma spray porosity, thus improving the adherence between coating and substrate. The corrosion behaviour of coatings of this type has been studied previously by Navas et al. [18], who showed that the partial melting process does not affect the corrosion rate of the plasma spray coating without a laser post-process.

This paper studies the wear behaviour of partially laser-melted coatings previously obtained by APS, focussing on the influence of two geometrical parameters of the coating: the angle between the laser tracks and sliding direction, and the percentage of melted surface. The authors have observed that the results obtained using sliding distances similar to those found in the literature for this type of coating and analogous test conditions are strongly influenced by run up process. For this reason, the sliding distance employed in this study was very high and the run-up process was studied for each test condition. Consequently, the wear rate and friction coefficient were compared under steady state conditions.

2. Experimental procedure

Tribological behaviour was studied using a block-on-ring wear test under lubricated conditions. The main coating studied, a NiCrBSi alloy deposited by plasma spray and partially melted by laser, was performed on ring specimens. A WC-Co coating was used on the block so as to obtain a harder counter face.

Two geometrical parameters of the partially melted coatings were studied: the percentage of surface melted, and the angle between the parallel laser tracks and the sliding direction. The track angles tested ranged between 11.25° and 78.75° , while the melted surfaces tested were between 16% and 66%. Every test was performed three times, reporting the average results and standard deviation when comparing the friction coefficient and wear rate.

The chemical composition of the NiCrBSi alloy studied is the shown in Table 1, according to analysis certificates of powder manufacturer. In a first manufacturing step, a 0.5 mm thickness of NiCrBSi alloy was deposited on a S355 J2G3 steel substrate with a blasted surface. The plasma spray process was performed using 75 l/min of N_2 as the primary plasmogen gas and 15 l/min of H_2 as the secondary plasmogen gas, both at a pressure of 3.4 bar. The powder feed rate was 8 kg/h and the distance between the nozzle and the surface was 100 mm, using an automatic carrier to apply a homogenous thickness of coating on the entire area of the steel substrate.

The second manufacturing step consisted in a grinding process to obtain an accurate coating thickness of 0.45 mm and homogeneous roughness. This procedure is absolutely necessary before the laser-melted post-process to ensure correct control of this process, especially the metallurgical bonding between coating and substrate.

The next manufacturing step consisted in the partial laser-melting process using a CO_2 laser operating in TEM 01* mode. The geometric shape performed to generate the partial melting consisted of parallel straight laser tracks. The power used was 1260 W at a processing speed of 335 mm/min, using 0.5 bar of argon as the protection gas. The distance of focalization was 8 mm, obtaining a track width of 1.48 mm. The last manufacturing process to obtain the ring specimens consisted of a new grinding process. This is necessary to ensure the final roughness of the surface and to homogenize the thickness of the coating to 0.35 mm. Due to the laser-melting process, the coating loses porosity and, resulting in a reduction in the thickness of the coating in the melted areas.

Figure 1 shows an end-manufactured specimen after the wear test. The wear scar produced during the wear test can be seen on right of the cylindrical face, along with the block counter face situated as in its

position during the test. The end-manufactured surface of the coating can be seen on left of the cylindrical face, where two different types of regions can be observed. One corresponds to non-melted areas, which have a high porosity, while the other corresponds to the laser-melted areas, which are non-porous, as can be seen in the detail of these regions in Figure 1.

The counter face block consisted of a C45E steel part with a WC coating obtained by laser cladding. This coating was manufactured using a CO₂ laser and lateral injection nozzle, using argon as the carrier gas.

The powder used had a chemical composition of 17% Co and 83% WC and angular shape with an average grain size of 43 μm .

The lubricant used in the wear tests contained an anti-wear additive and had a viscosity of 43.87 mm^2/s at 40°C and 6.481 mm^2/s at 100°C. The viscosity index of this oil is 96, according to ASTM D2270.

Wear tests were performed using a block-on-ring contact configuration, according to ASTM G77 standards. The partially melted NiCrBSi coating was performed on the ring specimen, with a final diameter of 55.7 mm. All tests were carried out under room temperature conditions, using a constant mass flow of 20 ml/min of lubricant applied over the contact area. The normal load applied was 400 N, which corresponds to 0.36 GPa of maximum contact pressure according to Euler's theory. The tested sliding speed was 3 m/s and the sliding distance was 122.5 km (equivalent to 700,000 cycles). The coefficient of friction (COF) was measured continuously using a torque sensor situated on the shaft of the tribometer. The wear rate was determined by measuring the loss in weight of the specimens, stopping the test every 100,000 cycles. The contact temperature was estimated as the temperature of the block specimen and the block holder measured with a monochromatic infra-red pyrometer on the side section of the block, near to the contact area.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were used to characterize the microstructure of the NiCrBSi coating in both regions, with and without laser post-treatment. The Vickers hardness of the NiCrBSi and WC-Co coatings was determined using a micro-durometer at 300gr of load for 15 s, according to ASTM E384 standards. A 1000X optical microscope was used to check the quality of the coatings with respect to the presence of pores and cracks. Roughness was determined for different areas of the coating using a contact profilometer.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Testing the coatings

Partial laser post-treatment generates two different areas on the coating, as can be seen in Figure 2a, which shows a cross section of the Ni alloy coating deposited by plasma spray and partially melted by laser. On the left, the melted area presents a homogeneous non-porous coating, with a metallurgical bonding between the Ni alloy and the steel substrate. The non-melted plasma spray area seen on the right presents high porosity due to the non-melted powder particles, and oxidation of powder particles during the APS process. No cracks have been detected in cross section and also in longitudinal section of melted tracks, as can be observed in figure 2a and figure 2b. This structure has been widely reported in the literature for this type of material and this technique of deposition and laser melting [19].

EDS analysis was made in order to determine hypothetical changes in chemical composition of the coating after laser melting process. Figure 3a shows the main results of EDS in 6 points analysed in a cross section of a melted track, at different distance to the surface coating. The similar chemical composition in the three points analysed in the NiCrBSi coating indicate that the main composition of the coating is not affected by the laser melting process, at least at depth of 300 μm to the surface. In order to study the dilution of the coating after laser melting process, EDS analysis was completed with a detailed test around to 350 μm to the coating surface. Figure 3b shows the results of X-rays counts of detailed test. The presence of iron varies from very low count, characteristic of 4.08% w.t of the NiCrBSi coating, up to very high values, characteristic of the steel used as substrate. The variation in iron counts are produced in a 35 microns thickness strip. Nickel and chromium counts vary also in the same 35 microns strip, which indicates a dilution around 10%.

EDS and SEM analysis of the microstructure in the melted areas revealed that the microstructure is formed by a metal matrix with a dendritic structure of Ni and low percentages of Cr and Fe (zones 3 in Figure 4) and an inter-dendritic lamellar phase of Ni and low percentages of Si (zones 2 in Figure 4). There are some very hard precipitates inside the metal matrix (zones 1 in Figure 4), formed by Cr. These precipitates are assumed to be chromium carbides and chromium borides due the relatively high levels of B and C in the alloy and the results of previous research studies in the literature [20-23].

Figure 5 shows the hardness profiles of the partially laser-melted plasma spray NiCrBSi coating and the WC-Co laser cladding coating used as a counter face in the wear test. The laser melting process increases

the hardness of the Ni alloy coating for every depth position on the cross section. Even after the NiCrBSi alloy has undergone the laser post-process, the counter face coating presents greater hardness.

The average roughness obtained was $R_a = 1.43 \mu\text{m}$ for the non-melted plasma spray areas and $R_a = 0.48 \mu\text{m}$ for the melted areas. The different roughness measured is caused by the porosity of the plasma areas.

Microstructural analysis and the hardness test evidenced similar behaviour to that of previous research studies in the literature for materials of this type [17, 18, 24, 25], which indicates that the coatings obtained present similar characteristics to those employed in studies.

3.2. Friction coefficient

The variation in the COF during a wear test is shown in Figure 5. One complete wear test consisting of 700,000 cycles is shown in this figure, each curve representing the COF values measured at each test step of 100,000 cycles. The X axis of Figure 6 represents the test duration of each test step. At the beginning of the test, during the first 30,000 cycles of the first test step, the measured COF presents high unstable values due to the run-up process. This run-up process is caused by the initial roughness of the two surfaces, which are removed under steady-state wear contact as a result of a loss of material or plastic deformation. Hence, greater the roughness and the higher the hardness of the surfaces, the slower run-up process and the greater the effects of this phenomenon will be.

During the first 5,000 cycles of each step, the COF shows a rising trend followed by a similar stable value for all steps. This behaviour is caused by the evolution of the viscosity of the lubricant during the test, which varies with the temperature. At the beginning of each test step, the temperature of the specimens and lubricant was around 20°C (room conditions). During the test, however, the contact area temperature increases up to 100°C after the first cycles of each step. The temperature of the lubricant accordingly increases during each test step due to the low mass flow employed and the thermal conductivity of the pipes in the tribometer. Although the COF stabilizes at 5,000 cycles, the recorded temperature needs 15,000 cycles to reach the steady state during the test. This lag between the steady state in COF measurements and temperature is caused by the distance between the real contact area and the point measured via the infrared pyrometer. The thermal conductivity in the counter face block and the tribometer holder causes a slight difference and lag between the contact temperature and the recorded value.

Figure 7 compares the COF for different geometry shapes of the laser-melted coating. The values represented on the charts were obtained as the average of the COF recorded at the steady region for each test step, discarding the first cycles of each step. Standard deviations are represented for each test condition. 0% of melted surface represent the NiCrBSi plasma spray coating without the laser post-process. Analysis of the percentage of melted surface results does not reveal any significant influence on COF behaviour. The COF increase slightly only when the melted surface reaches the highest values, as can be seen in the graph on the left in Figure 6. However, plasma spray without laser post-treatment presents a lower COF. In contrast, laser track angle is seen to influence the COF, an increasing laser track angle increasing the COF and the standard deviation.

This behaviour indicates that reducing the porous areas of the coating does not significantly affect lubrication conditions, at least in melted surfaces below 56%. Low laser track angles produce a more gradual contact transition between the laser-melted areas, which have a harder and a more homogenous microstructure and the plasma spray areas, which have greater porosity, resulting in a lower COF. In contrast, high laser track angles produce a more abrupt change in the contact between the plasma spray areas and the melted areas leading to an increase in the COF and the noise recorded during the test, as well as an increase in the standard deviation. Plasma spray without the laser post-process, does not result in transitions between the areas with different properties and hence the recorded COF are the lowest.

3.3. Wear

The total wear results of the three replicates of each test conditions has a high variability, as can be seen in Figure 8, which represents the evolution in wear recorded for the three replicates for one of the test conditions. In spite of the higher variability observed, the three tests show a linear behaviour and similar gradient in the interval from 200,000 to 700,000 cycles, which is a sign of a similar wear rate during this period. At the beginning, the run-up process causes very high uncontrolled loss of material at the surfaces due to the high roughness of the coating and the higher hardness of the counter face coating. This behaviour was observed for all test conditions and impeded the comparison of the total wear measurements. Figure 9 shows the cross section and surface of the coating before (image a) and after (image b) wear test, where the reduction in roughness can be observed, especially in the melted areas. Due to the high variability observed in the total wear results for the tested sliding distance, the analysis of wear was carried out by comparing the average recorded wear rate for each test conditions between

200,000 and 700,000 cycles. Run-up wear results were not considered to compare the behaviour of the different geometries of the laser post-process, seeing as the main objective of this research was the study of steady-state wear behaviour.

Figure 10 shows the average recorded wear rate for different percentages of melted surface and track angle, along with the standard deviation. In contrast with the results observed for the COF in Figure 6, the track angle does not present significant effects on the wear rate. The observed differences in the wear rate for different track angles are similar to the standard deviation calculated, which indicates that the influence of the track angle on wear rate is not significant. Despite the high variability observed, the percentage of melted surface affects the trend of the wear rate. The wear rate decreases with increasing melted surface, reaching a minimum at 46%, while for higher values of melted surface, the wear rate increases slightly. For low melted percentages, the wear rate also presents greater variability due to the predominance of non-homogeneous plasma spray areas in the coating. In non-homogeneous materials, discrete wear debris can be detached from the coating via an abrasive wear mechanism by brittle fracture [26] due to the numerous cracks in plasma spray structures. For high percentages of melted surface, the reduction in the porous area causes poor lubrication conditions, as can be observed by analysing the COF shown in Figure 6, as well as increasing wear on the melted areas. The optimum percentage for minimizing the wear rate is hence 46%, because, under these conditions, the two opposing effects described previously are balanced. However, the differences between 36 and 56% are very low, and the measured values are similar to the standard deviation.

Wear was produced on the NiCrBSi coating, on both areas, laser-melted and non-melted, as can be seen in Figure 11a. SEM analysis of the wear scar on the plasma spray coating indicates a mainly abrasive wear mechanism. Figures 11c and 11d show the wear scar on a melted area (Fig. 11c) and a plasma spray area of the coating, with a marked debris particle (Fig. 11d). EDS analysis of this type of particle (Fig. 11b) indicates that it is composed of tungsten carbide originating from the counter face coating, given the high concentration of W and Co. The presence of these WC debris particles indicates a three-body abrasion mechanism. Furthermore, the WC particles embedded in the counter face coating, as shown in Figure 11, produce abrasive wear both in the NiCrBsi rings and the WC blocks (three-body abrasion mechanism).

SEM analysis of the wear scar on the counter face blocks, shown in Figure 12, indicates that WC particles are embedded in the coating, and can produce a two-body wear mechanism. During the wear test, the WC

particles embedded in the coating, become detached, and thus causing the three-body abrasive mechanism described previously.

4. Conclusions

The partial laser-melting post-process on NiCrBSi plasma spray coatings has been shown to improve wear behaviour. The lowest recorded wear rate corresponds to 46% of melted surface, although the differences recorded between 36%, 46% and 56% were very small. The laser-melted post-process generates a harder coating than plasma spray process, but removes the characteristic porous surface of this type of coating. Above 46% of melted surface, the lower porosity of the coating lead to poor lubrication conditions, resulting in a slightly increase in wear rate. Melted surfaces of below 46% lead to greater wear rates due to the non-homogenous plasma spray structure, but do not improve lubrication conditions, as suggested by the fact of measuring the same COF for 16% to 56%.

The laser track angle does not show a significant influence on the wear rate under the tested conditions. However, the track angle does affect the COF due to of the transition in the contact between the melted areas and the plasma spray areas. High laser track angles increase the COF and the variability due to the fact that the transition between the two areas, which have different properties, is more abrupt.

The run-up process was found to be a very important wear phenomenon. Wear and COF analysis showed that the first 30,000 cycles of the test correspond to run-up, as well as to a large and high variability in wear and COF. For these reasons, the sliding distance tested in this paper was greater than those of previous studies. Furthermore, the results of this study are not comparable with previous research studies in the literature because the latter do not remove run-up data, in addition to considering a sliding distance that is too short to minimize the effects of the run-up process.

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References

- [1] H.-J. Rätzer-Scheibe, U. Schulz; The effects of heat treatment and gas atmosphere on the thermal conductivity of APS and EB-PVD PYSZ thermal barrier coatings; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 201 (2007), 7880-7888
- [2] M.A. Helminiak, N.M. Yanar, F.S. Pettit, T.A. Taylor, G.H. Meier; The behavior of high-purity, low-density air plasma sprayed thermal barrier coatings; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 204 (2009), 793-796
- [3] C.H. Hager Jr., J.H. Sanders, S. Sharma; Unlubricated gross slip fretting wear of metallic plasma-sprayed coatings for Ti6Al4V surfaces; *Wear*, 265 (2008), 439-451
- [4] J. Rodríguez, A. Martín, R. Fernández, J.E. Fernández; experimental study of the wear performance of NiCrBSi thermal spray coatings; *War* 255 (2003), 950-955
- [5] G Akdogan, T.A Stolarski, S Tobe; Surface fatigue of molybdenum and Al-bronze coatings in unlubricated rolling/sliding contact; *Wear* 253 (2002), 319-330
- [6] Kanchan Kumari, K. Anand, Michelangelo Bellacci, Massimo Giannozzi; Effect of microstructure on abrasive wear behavior of thermally sprayed WC-10Co-4Cr coatings; *Wear*, 268 (2010), 1309-1319
- [7] E. Fernández, J.M. Cuetos, R. Vijande, A. Rincón; Comparison of wear behaviour of plasma-sprayed Al₂O₃ coatings with and without laser treatment; *Tribol. Int.*, 29 (1996), 477-485
- [8] R. Vijande, F.J. Belzunce, E. Fernández, M.C. Becarés, A. Rincón; Wear and microstructure in fine ceramic coatings; *Wear*, 148 (1991), 221-233
- [9] B. Torres, M.A. Garrido, A. Rico, P. Rodrigo, M. Campo, J. Rams; Wear behaviour of thermal spray Al/SiCp coatings; *Wear*, 268 (2010), 828-836
- [10] T. Gómez-del Río, M.A. Garrido, J.E. Fernández, M. Cadenas, J. Rodríguez; Influence of the deposition techniques on the mechanical properties and microstructure of NiCrBSi coatings; *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, 204 (2008), 304-312
- [11] C. Navas, R. Colaço, J. de Damborenea, R. Vilar; Abrasive wear behaviour of laser clad and flame sprayed-melted NiCrBSi coatings; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 200 (2006), 6854-6862
- [12] N. Serres, F. Hlawka, S. Costil, C. Langlade, F. Machi; Microstructures and environmental assessment of metallic NiCrBSi coatings manufactured via hybrid plasma spray process; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 205 (2010), 1039-1046
- [13] M. Laribi, N. Mesrati, A.B. Vannes, D. Treheux; Adhesion and residual stresses determination of thermally sprayed molybdenum on steel; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 166 (203), 483-489

- [14] L. Prchlik, S. Sampath; Effect of the microstructure of thermally sprayed coatings on friction and wear response under lubricated and dry sliding conditions; *Wear*, 262 (2007), 11–23
- [15] R. González, M. Cadenas, R. Fernández, J.L. Cortizo, E. Rodríguez; Wear behaviour of flame sprayed NiCrBSi coating remelted by flame or by laser, *Wear*, 262 (2007), 301-307
- [16] N. Serres, F. Hlawka, S. Costil, C. Langlade, F. Machi; Microstructures and mechanical properties of metallic NiCrBSi and composite NiCrBSi–WC layers manufactured via hybrid plasma/laser process; *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 257 (2011), 5132-5137
- [17] Felgueroso, D., Vijande, R., Cuetos, J.M., Tucho, R., Hernández, A.; Parallel laser melted tracks: Effects on the wear behaviour of plasma sprayed Ni-based coatings; *Wear*, 264 (2008), 257-263
- [18] C. Navas, R. Vijande, J.M. Cuetos, M.R. Fernández, J. de Damborenea; Corrosion behaviour of NiCrBSi plasma sprayed coatings partially melted with laser; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 201 (2006), 776-785
- [19] M.P. Planche, H. Liao, B. Normand, C. Coddet; Relationships between NiCrBSi particle characteristics and corresponding coating properties using different thermal spraying process ; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 200 (2005), 2465–2473
- [20] J.M. Miguel, J.M. Guilemany, S. Vizcaíno; Tribological study of NiCrBSi coating obtained by different processes; *Tribol. Int.*, 36 (2003), 181–187
- [21] D.W. Zhang, T.C. Lei, J.-g. Zhang, J.-h. Ouyang; The effects of heat treatment on microstructure and erosion properties of laser surface-clad Ni-base alloy ; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 115 (1999), 176–183
- [22] Q. Li, D. Zhang, T. Lei, Ch. Chen, W. Chen; Comparison of laser-clad and furnace-melted Ni-based alloy microstructures; *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 137 (2001), 122–135
- [23] A. Conde, F. Zubiri, J. de Damborenea; Cladding of Ni–Cr–B–Si coatings with a high power diode laser; *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, A334 (2002), 233–238
- [24] M. Cadenas, R. Vijande, H.J. Montes, J.M. Sierra; Wear behaviour of laser cladded and plasma sprayed WC-Co coatings; *Wear*, 212 (1997), 244–253
- [25] R. González, M.A. García, I. Peñuelas, M. Cadenas, M. del Rocío Fernández, A. Hernández Battez, D. Felgueroso; Microstructural study of NiCrBSi coatings obtained by different processes; *Wear*, 263 (2007), 619–624
- [26] I. M. Hutchings; *Tribology Friction and Wear of Engineering Materials*; first ed., Edward Arnold, 1992

Ni	71.7
Cr	15.7
B	3.35
Si	4.27
Fe	4.08
C	0.81

Table 1 Chemical composition (w.t. %) of the NiCrBSi alloy employed.

Highlights

- Influence of two geometrical parameters on tribological behaviour was studied.
- Pure sliding wear tests at lubricated contact were performed.
- Partial melting process reduces wear, 46% of melted surface produces minimum wear.
- Partial melting process increases COF, as greater track angle, greater COF.

Figures

Fig. 1 Ring specimen with a NiCrBSi coating obtained by plasma spray and partially melted by laser, and the counter face specimen. Detail of the partially melted surface.

Fig. 2 Cross section (a) of the NiCrBSi coating. Laser-melted track on the left and non-melted plasma spray on the right. Longitudinal section (b) of the NiCrBSi coating in the melted track.

Fig. 3 a) Main chemical composition of melted coating obtained by EDS analysis. b) Detail of EDS analysis of the dilution zone.

Fig. 4 SEM image of a cross section of the NiCrBSi coating in the laser-melted area.

Fig. 5 Micro-hardness profiles obtained in the cross section of the coatings.

Fig. 6 Evolution of the COF during a complete wear test of $7 \cdot 10^5$ cycles at a 45° track angle and 36% melted surface.

Fig. 7 COF as a function of the % of melted surface for a 45° laser track, 400 N normal load and 3 m/s sliding speed (left). COF as a function of the laser track angle for 36% melted surface, 400 N normal load and 3 m/s sliding speed (right).

Fig. 8 Comparison between the wear recorded for the three tests under the same test conditions: 45° laser track angle, 36% melted surface, 400N normal load and 3 m/s sliding speed.

Fig. 9 Cross section and surface of the NiCrBSi coating. a) Before the wear test, with ground finish. b) After the wear test.

Fig. 10 Wear rate as a function of the % of melted surface for a 45° laser track, 400 N normal load and 3 m/s sliding speed (left). Wear rate as a function of the laser track angle for 36% melted surface, 400 N normal load and 3 m/s sliding speed (right).

Fig. 11 SEM analysis of the wear scar on the NiCrBSi alloy. a) Overview of the scar on the left, and non-tested surface on the right. b) EDS analysis of the wear debris marked on d. c) Detail of the scar on the melted surface. d) Detail of the Scar on the plasma spray surface and detail of the wear debris.

Fig. 12 Detail of the wear scar on the counter face block with WC particles embedded in the surface.

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